

Analysis of Negotiating with Trauma In Novel Breath Eyes Memory By Edwidge Danticat by Zeitha

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Abstract

Trauma is often the main theme in a literary work. Just like in the novel *Breath Eyes Edwidge's Memory Danticat*. The main problem in the novel focuses on the trauma of sexuality that women from the Caco family have and their efforts to negotiate and make peace with the trauma they experience. The purpose of this research is to dissect any type of trauma and what efforts are made by the characters to compromise with the trauma they have. The results of the study show that Haitian women must experience the trauma caused by sexual harassment and virginity tests. Despite the persistent pain, these women try to negotiate by giving testimony and accepting all the causes that are the root of the trauma. They testify with their descendants and some go to see a therapist. In addition, Sophie shows acceptance of her mother's existence so that she can slowly come to terms with her trauma.

Keywords *trauma, negotiation, Breath Eyes Memory, Edge Danticat*

INTRODUCTION

Life is not always about happiness, sometimes there are always very painful events that befall each individual or collectively. At this horrific and traumatic time, many people try to push it further back into their most hidden minds. It is normal to hide or cover up these memories in self-defense, forgetting and suppressing bad emotional experiences. However, many people put bitter experiences or bad events that happen around them into writing. From this, literary works with the theme of traumatic events were born that explore the trauma of the characters. One of the writers who are very thick with this theme is Edwidge Danica.

Edge Danticat is a Haitian-American novelist who has produced many works of fiction with the theme of trauma and memory. This novel tends to emphasize the issue of sexual harassment and violence and how they are related to the mother-daughter relationship of the main character.

METHOD

Collection methods and techniques are a set of methods or techniques that are an extension of the human senses because the goal is to collect empirical facts related to the research problem. In this case, the object of research is the novel *Breath Eyes Memory* by Edwidge _ Danticat. This novel was read several times to deepen and clarify the story content of the novel.

The source of research data is the novel *Breath Eyes Memory* by Edwidge _ Danticat. The data of this study consisted of primary data and secondary data. Primary data itself contains evidence in the form of phrases, sentences, and paragraphs obtained from the novel *Breath Eyes Memory* that refers to trauma concepts from Cathy Caruth and

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Trauma depicted in *Breath, Eyes, Memory* focuses on the trauma of sexuality problems experienced by Haitian women which are depicted through women in the Caco family. Furthermore, to fully understand the complexities of trauma to the Caco woman, it is necessary to take a closer look at the sources of this trauma. This section builds on the socio-cultural context of Haitian women's sexuality that serves as a backdrop for the experiences of traumatized individuals in *Breath, Eyes, Memory*.

The paradox of women's sexuality becomes a source of trauma for women in this novel. This trauma is related to the cultural trauma that deeply affects Haitian women, which causes problems and conflicts that are so personal in the lives of women in *Breath, Eyes, Memory*. Thus, the trauma is very influential and affects Haitian women as a group, because in this case the trauma is passed down from mother to daughter. Trauma Experienced by Characters in Novel *Breath, Eyes Memory*, can not be separated from a strongly patriarchal culture, where women have a position determined by society, especially men. Trauma is created because women themselves cannot influence them and are confined by tradition.

CONCLUSION

The trauma of Haitian female sexuality builds up from several different traumas in *Breath, Eyes, Memory*. These individual aspects result from trauma to women's sexuality, sexual violence, and

surrogate mothers. This individual trauma causes great pain for the Caco women in the novel, and to overcome this some women use narrating or sharing stories with others as a method of negotiation.

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